

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HOMONYMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES FOR METHODOLOGICAL PURPOSES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the comparison between Uzbek and English and Russian homonyms languages. In English, the nature of homographs and homophones are different. It's connected with differences in spelling guidelines. If in Russian the leading one is morphological principle of writing (the principle of uniformity of writing morphemes), then in English the overwhelming most spellings are subject to historical and traditional principles.

Homophone is a word that is pronounced the same as another word but differs in meaning and may differ in spelling. Usually when we speak about homophones we mean homophones inside one language. But there are also homophones that belong to different languages or interlanguage homophones. In this research we studied homophones between Uzbek and English and Russian languages.

Continuous sampling of all dictionaries showed that in English genetically unrelated homonyms-nouns make up a larger number in relation to Uzbek language. This indicates a high semantic productivity of genetically unrelated homonyms in English language. For comparison: in Uzbek language has 32 homonyms, while in English there are 72 of them. There are several English homonyms-nouns with 24 meanings. It's unique

homonymous series of sounds. This line consists of two chains. It should be noted that the chain of the first

meaning includes archaisms, American slangisms, terminological, idiomatic meanings noted in dictionaries. This fact indicates a fairly active ability English words in the formation of homonyms.

Comparison methods need to be developed teaching English homonyms to Russian speakers. We can say that the comparative typology languages in general have an applied value for linguodidactics and is in demand in those cases when it is necessary to overcome speech intervention, as well as in the formation language competence of students. Note that homonymy is usually one of the factors of interlingual and intralingual intervention. Interlingual interference in business homonyms appear

randomly pronunciation and/or spelling of words differently languages (the so-called "false friends translator"). Problems of intralinguistic interference the problem of differentiating polysemy and homonymy.

Among the meanings of pitch homonyms, there is a semantic disconnection between the chains, for example, pitch in the third meaning has branches -points "a" and "b": a - to throw (the ball) to the batter in a game of baseball: to pitch curves and fast balls' - to loft (a golf ball) so that it alights with little roll.

The reason for dividing into two points is intrinsic motivation, belonging to one archaism. In addition, observations showed that the word in question has high productivity in both synchronous and diachronic aspects. The analyzed genetically unrelated homonyms have different semantic productivity. In the group of a high degree of semantic productivity, we included homonyms-nouns with 30 to 20 semantic meanings; in the group with average semantic productivity, homonyms are nouns with a numerical value from 20 to 10. Values; in a group with a low degree of semantic productivity - homonyms having from 10 to 2

values. It should be noted that in Uzbek except in isolated cases, almost never happens monographic research in the field of lexico-semantic, pragmatic signs of homonyms. No specific description and information about homonyms in dictionaries. The point is that dictionaries The Uzbek language is still compiled in basis of written artistic language. Meanwhile, the materials of the artistic language are only

"the tip iceberg". The actual problem of the Uzbek language is the compilation of dictionaries with the largest number of homonymous series covering all spheres of life, especially in oral speech. This will allow researchers rely on all existential forms: artistic language, dialects, professional vocabulary, jargon, slang, barbarism, vulgarity and exotic vocabulary. Studies have shown that in the dictionary "Uzbek tiling homonymlar lugati" ("Dictionary homonyms of the Uzbek language"), number genetically unrelated homonyms from one to five series members. So, the homonyms of the word zil (in Uzbek) - three rows. Each row consists of one member and belongs to separate groups according to the original language. In the first meaning the word zil is borrowed from German and is used in the sense of "og'ir" (heavy). That the second homonym is borrowed from Turkish language and means "musiqqa asbobi" (musical tool). The third homonym zil is borrowed from Arabic meaning "kamsitish" (humiliation). Genetically unrelated homonyms the words alif, gas, termite, farm make up two row of the same name, having in the first row - 1, in the second - 2 unmotivated values.

1. Alif1 (Arabic) 1. "The first letter of Arabic alphabet." Alif (Russian) 1. "Linseed oil". 2. "Hashish butter." 2. Gas1 (Persian-Tajik) 1. "Measure of length". Gas2 (French) 1. Fashion. 2. "Silk fabric". From them examples, we can conclude that the second line homonyms have two meanings, but from a semantic point of view there is an internal connection. Behind for example, the homonym alif2 is used in the meanings "linseed oil" and "hash oil". common, unifying these meanings are the same "oil".

Second component *sema* - belonging of "oil" to a particular plant. The words *gas*, *thermite* are also observed above situation. The appearance of these homonyms may be seen as the result of a relationship between integral and differential *semas*, which led to value formation independently of each other. Among the units considered in terms of semantic productivity, it is necessary to note the words which cannot be grouped together.

In this regard, the phenomenon of English-Russian interlanguage homonymy

requires special consideration, i.e. the so-called "false friends of the translator". This figurative expression is traditionally used to denote

lexemes in tune with each other, but inconsistent in meaning in two different

languages.

For example, the English word *artist* - a person who creates paintings or drawings as a profession or hobby, is consonant with the Russian word *артист*; *book* - a written or printed work consisting of pages glued or sewn together along one side and bound in covers, consonant with the Russian word - *бук* (type of tree); *boy* - a male child or youth. - cf. Russian *бой*; *box* - a container with a flat base and sides,

typically square or rectangular and having a lid

- English in Russian *бокс* (kind of sport); *bread*

- food made of flour, water, and yeast mixed together and baked - cf. Russian *бред*

(nonsense); *capital* - the city or town that unctons as the seat of government and

administrative centre of a country or region - cf. Russian *капитал*; *clever* - smart - cf. Russian *клевер* (plant); *look* - direct one's gaze toward someone or something or in a specified direction - cf. Russian *лук* (vegetable) and many

others. The phenomenon of lexical homonymy has the character of a linguistic universal and therefore the ontological properties of lexical homonyms in English and Russian are generally comparable: their sources, types and stylistic

functions in speech are similar. However, along with this, the English homonyms, in comparison with the Russians, have some specific features. The differences

between homographs and homophones are particularly clear. So, despite the fact that there are significantly more homonyms in English than in Russian, their collision in the text occurs relatively rarely. This is due to the fact that in the process of speech implementation, homonymy, fixed at the level of the language system, is removed as a result of shaping. For example, most English verbs that are homonymous to each other in the infinitive form do not coincide in other forms. In the form of an infinitive, they are used only in certain cases, for example, if they stand in Present Indefinite Tense or Future Indefinite Tense, coinciding in sound and writing with the forms of the 1st and 2nd person singular and plural and 3rd person plural.

In general, the nature of the differences between Russian and English homonyms

rooted mainly in morphology and literature formation. If English is an analytical language, then the Russian language functions as a language synthetic structure with a tendency to analytics. This means that the synthetic grammatical device prevails in Russian. Language and inflection are actively used. English, inflection has lost its meaning and function. This has led to a sharp increase the possibility of homonyms appearing as the result of syntactic transposition. Transition of words from one part of speech to another. For example, the beak (the jaws of a bird together with their horny cover) - beak (to touch and rub beak on beak), bowl (bowl-shaped structure) - bowl (roll the ball), break (interrupt sequence, stroke or continuous that both languages are to some extent distanced from the phonetic principle, which requires, as you know, the coincidence of sound and spelling. In other words, the sound and spelling of words and morphemes in Russian and English do not coincide approximately to the same extent, but the nature of these discrepancies is different. Thus, if homographs and homophones in Russian arise under the influence of living phonetic processes, then in English they are the result of historical processes. This is directly reflected in the teaching strategy of Russian and English homographs and homophones. If in teaching Russian homographs and homophones the emphasis should be on the study of the synchronic aspect of phonetics, then in teaching English - on the study of the diachronic aspect of phonetics.

In linguistic literature, the terms "homonyms" homonymy of language units" and "homonymy" used. In the dissertation,

such an understanding homonymy is criticized. Homonymy of language units is a more general concept. This term in lexical meanings covers the whole process of homonymy, which exists in the language. These include homonymous morphemes and root morphemes, as well as affixal morphemes, i.e. this process takes place on the morpheme level. The second group of homonymy arises in word level. We conditionally divide this current into two more groups, proper homonyms - lexical and lexico-grammatical and, together with them, homonymous phenomena: homofoms, homophones, homographs. The third large group at the level of phrases is phenomena are divided into two subgroups: combined and phraseological homonymy. Fourth group homonymy consists of homonymy of sentences. This phenomenon can be called syntactic homonymy. This current process is divided into two subgroups: homonymy of simple sentences and homonymy of complex prepositions. The second section describes homonymous phenomena. Different researchers interpret differently similar phenomena. Based on factual material, some of them prove that homonymous phenomena exist in the modern Uzbek language. Others don't recognize the existence of homonymous phenomena in modern Uzbek (M.Mirtajiev). There are also scholars who recognize these phenomena, but to attribute homonymous phenomena to homonyms. We don't belong to the supporters both the first and second groups, recognizing that homonymous phenomena exist in language, in form and function are similar to homonyms, but do not coincide with them in meaning.

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